

Establishment of Effective Internal Audit Function: Recommendations for Best Practice

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This paper¹, which is in the light of the last trends in internal auditing, aims to explain the challenges and major issues in establishment of an effective internal audit (IA) function to achieve value-added IA activities as a value-added service center. This paper also discusses the current internal auditing environment in Turkey considered for the needs and expectations of stakeholders and new legislations. In the next five years, five emerging activities for internal auditing may be taken into consideration, namely, the review of corporate governance process, auditing of enterprise risk management (ERM) processes, addressing linkage of strategy and company performance, the ethics audits, and the migration to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), they will be the major focus areas for internal auditing. The qualifications of IA staff, status within the corporation, setting up of the functional and administrative reporting lines, relationship with the audit committee of the board of directors, and the content of IA charter must be sufficient for assurance of the IA function's effectiveness and objectivity. The effective communication channels among management, audit committee, and IA become more important and must be operated in a consistent manner that accurately contributes to preventing potential future financial crisis and the effectiveness of risk management (RM). Ten main imperatives of change for IA can be summarized as emphasizing RM and governance, addressing key stakeholder priorities, and optimizing IA resources. Based on professional practices, international standards of Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA), best practices, and the relevant recommendations have been made by the authors for practitioners and stakeholders.

Keywords: internal audit (IA), audit committee, enterprise risk management (ERM)

JEL Classification Codes: G30, M42

Introduction

Considering the globalization and challenges in the economy, boards and audit committees are interested in a "real time" overarching view of the control environment from internal audit (IA) rather than audit reports on individual areas of the business. The IA departments enhance corporate capability and productivity by providing management with proficiency in developing and maintaining an effective internal control environment and also by conducting efficient and effective audits. In that respect, building a quality IA

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department is essential to contributing to the corporate mission. The IA activity should contribute to the organization's governance process by evaluating and improving the process, through which values and goals are established and communicated. The accomplishment of goals is monitored; accountability is ensured; and values are preserved. Measuring efficiency in IA is commonly a straightforward and reasonable process. Measuring the inputs working hours or some other quantitative measures is comparatively simple. However, outputs are supposed to take on relevance to the organization rather than a simple number of audits conducted, or disregarding outputs and simply quantifying inputs. Effectiveness is, to a certain extent, different. Based on the definition of effectiveness, management of IA needs to first establish a reasonable, achievable, and relevant mission statement with appropriate goals and strategies. This mission should be compatible with the corporate culture, roles, responsibilities, management's goals, and strategic objectives. In that case, effectiveness could be seen as a measure of how well IA accomplishes the mission, as measured by how well it has achieved its goals associated with the mission statement.

It is a fundamental issue for internal auditors to have an organization and structure, which grant their independence within the corporate framework. It is usually the case that internal auditors are also the employees of the corporation. In this respect, the reporting relationship should be established with enough authority given to chief audit executive (CAE). CAE should be responsible for providing essential internal auditing coverage at an executive level. Such a reporting relationship has been initiated as a mandatory guideline by the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA). Lately, IIA has issued numerous practice advisories to deal with organizational independence, boards of directors, and audit committees².

Corporations have different internal auditing needs depending on the nature, size, and complexity of the entity. Thus, the particular status of the entity will govern the organizational structure of the internal auditing department. According to Jepsen (1979), there is a common organizational structure of the IA department to report directly to the corporation's senior financial officer on a daily basis. In addition to this, the department has a dotted-line³ relationship with the chairman or president.

The qualifications of IA staff, status within the corporation, reporting lines, and relationship with the audit committee of the board of directors must be sufficient for assurance of the effectiveness and objectivity of IA function. The internal auditors should consider their audit findings in the context of the organization's financial statements and they should also coordinate their activities with the activities of the independent auditing. IIA gives guidance on the establishment of an effective IA function by supporting the stakeholders with practice advisories. In this paper, major IIA recommendations are discussed and interpreted in the following sections to provide tips for a successful implementation for the establishment of an IA function.

Literature Review

Relevant literature focuses mostly on analyzing the changes and impact on the financial scandals over the IA's development. Hermanson, Carcello, and Raghunandan (2005) considered that the changes in internal auditing were related to the Enron and WorldCom financial failures and the related legislative and media interest in internal control and corporate governance. They found that budget, staffing levels, meetings with the

² They are: PA 1110-1 "organizational independence"; PA 1110-2 "CAE reporting lines"; PA 2060-1 "reporting to the board and senior management"; and PA 2060-2 "relationship with the audit committee". For further detailed information, please visit <http://www.theiia.org>.

³ The meaning of dotted-line relationship is a less frequent contact but a clear access to the top management, chairman, or president.

audit committee, and meeting length of IA increased noticeably during the period of financial crisis.

Smith (2002) discussed the necessity of strengthening the IA's position in the corporations by specific skills training of human resources. Smith (2002) mainly promoted the idea of reconstruction of IA departments. According to him, one of the most important causes of such big corporate failures was the outsourcing of the IA activity⁴. In addition, the importance of frequent audit committee meetings with detailed discussions with both IA and external audit was also indicated in the literature⁵.

Price Waterhouse Coopers (2007) conducted a survey on internal auditing and new trends. The major purpose of this survey is to identify the main trends that IA will have in its next evolution. Regarding the conclusions of this survey, the key issues are summarized as follows: Firstly, IA departments should adopt an IA's approach which is truly risk based. This is recommended if the internal auditors want to remain the key elements in risk management (RM) process and provide management-relevant and value-added advices. Secondly, the survey indicates that there are five particular trends—globalization, changes in RM, technological evaluation, organizational skills and talent, and changing role of IA. Hence, all these surveys and academic works show that a strong impact on IA functions in the coming years will be inevitable. It is essential to understand these trends and their inferences so that IA will be able to provide required assistance to the general management regarding the process of RM. In this way, IA function could provide added value to the organization in the end.

According to Leech (2009), during the recent period of global financial crisis, the internal auditors are successful in assessing and reporting on RM, unfortunately, they are unsuccessful in identifying and reporting the deficiencies that have been threatening the efficiency of RM within a reasonable time. In relation to such arguments, the IIA has revised the IA standards which have been applicable since the January 1st of 2009. The major issues and changes in the revised version of standards are designed to enhance the role and contribution of IA in monitoring, assessing, and reporting the effectiveness of conducting of a RM process⁶.

Analyzing the outcomes of the above-presented studies, it becomes clear that IA needs to redefine their priorities by adapting the scope of traditional objectives to those generated by the context of global financial crisis. In this new context, the professional staff will play an important role in coordinating the IA activities. IA activities have to be directed and conducted with a reference framework that is well established within the involvement and responsibility of CAE.

On the other hand, Bota-Avram, Pop, and Bota-Avram (2009) argued that even if the IA would be directed and conducted with highest efficiency and evaluation of the effectiveness of RM, it would not be able to avoid the crisis without the support of the audit committee and the management. In this situation, the effective communication channels among management, audit committee, and IA become more important and must be operated in a consistent manner that accurately contributes to preventing potential future financial crisis.

In order to capture the global trends, needs, and expectations of IA profession, IIA organized the global IA

⁴ Smith (2002, p. 13) argued that "Outsourced auditors often do not achieve the same understanding of the business and the people performing the everyday business transactions like internal auditors do".

⁵ For detailed information, please refer to: Glater and Treaster (2002); Hennessey and Whitman (2002); and Lublin (2002).

⁶ In the revised structure, it becomes completely necessary to establish a reference framework in assessing and reporting the effectiveness of RM. The main objective of this framework is the transmission of the necessary skills for internal auditors to guarantee compliance with IIA standards, mostly in the context of an environment so threatened by the global financial crisis phenomena that have generated such unexpected costs.

survey in 2010⁷. The results of IIA survey indicate five emerging activities for internal auditing in the next five years. The first one is about the review of corporate governance process. The second one is auditing of enterprise risk management (ERM) processes. The third one is addressing linkage of strategy and company performance. The fourth one is the ethics audits. And finally, the migration to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) will be the major focus areas for internal auditing.

In this paper, the above-mentioned key issues are discussed in the following sections from the perspective of the establishment of an effective IA function to cope with such new trends, needs, and expectations of related parties and stakeholders. Furthermore, some recommendations are made for achieving best practices.

Establishment of an Effective IA Function

The very first step in the process of the establishment of an IA function is the approval of IA charter. The major intention of the IA charter is to plausibly document the audit endorsement together with the powers it grants to carry out IA activities on behalf of the top management and the audit committee.

IIA provides professional practice advisories⁸ for best practices in line with the IIA standards. The charter is supposed to define the framework within which IA can operate independently. The charter should also ensure that IA's responsibilities do not limit its objectivity. In addition, the charter should set up the functional and administrative reporting lines of IA. The charter should also specify that IA has a direct access to the audit committee. The audit committee should evaluate and approve the charter annually, and proper modifications to the charter should be made considering the changes in the roles and responsibilities of IA management and team. Kagermann, Kinney, Küting, and Weber (2008) stated that the board of directors could fulfill its responsibility of establishing an effective IA function with a carefully developed audit mandate and charter.

Singh (2011) stated that in order to establish a comprehensive and balanced internal auditing function, the audit committee and CAE should consider the 10 imperatives of change (see Table 1). He segregated these change imperatives into three major categories (see Table 1). The first category is mainly about RM. IA function should develop a strategic vision and mission to conduct its fieldwork depending on risk-based IA plan. Singh (2011) also argued that there would be an increase in the involvement of IA functions to more strategic issues as the trends in IA are shown in Figure 1. The second category is related to communication skills and relationship with the audit committee. The IA function should have a direct access to the audit committee and they are required to meet regularly and frequently to monitor and focus on strategic issues on time. The third category defines the technical aspects of IA function such that they need to enhance their position by training and using audit tools and technological developments⁹ to optimize internal audit resources.

⁷ There are 13,500 responses from 107 countries and the results are summarized in five major IIA reports, namely: (1) characteristic of an IA activity; (2) core competencies for today's internal auditors; (3) measuring the value of internal auditing; (4) what is next for internal auditing?; and (5) imperatives for change. These reports are available on the website (<http://www.theiia.org>) of IIA.

⁸ Please refer to: Institute of Internal Auditors (2001a, 2001b); Institute of Internal Auditors (2002a, 2002b); and Institute of Internal Auditors (2005).

⁹ For further information on the role, effect, and contribution of the new technological developments and the modern Computer-Assisted Auditing Tools and Techniques (CAATs) upon the IA function and IA resources, please refer to Coderre (2009).

Figure 1. Trends in IA. Source: Columbus Advisory (2011).

Regarding the technical skills, “understanding the business” is ranked as the most important overall technical skill in the IIA’s (2010) survey. This is needed especially for a solid understanding of the business that is crucial for internal auditing to effectively identify emerging risk and control issues. In terms of core knowledge areas, survey outcomes of IIA (2010) showed the continuing importance of possessing knowledge of auditing, IA standards, ethics and fraud awareness, and ERM for internal auditors. The 10 imperatives of change for IA are shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Ten Imperatives of Change for IA

Group	Ten imperatives of change
Emphasizing RM and governance	Sharpen your focus on RM and governance Conduct a more responsive and flexible risk-based audit plan Develop a strategic vision for IA Focus, monitor, and report on IA’s value
Addressing key stakeholder priorities	Strengthen audit committee communications and relationships View compliance with the IIA’s international standards for the professional practice of internal auditing as mandatory
Optimizing IA resources	Acquire and develop top talent Enhance training for IA activities Take advantage of expanding service provider membership Step up your use of audit technology and tools

Note. Source: Singh (2011).

IA Functions as a Value-Added Service Center

Similar to all the other departments, IA functions are subjected to the basic rules of business. In other words, audit fieldworks must be performed cost-consciously. The existing IA resources must be deployed in a targeted and results-maximizing approach within the assigned budget. The CAE has the key responsibility for

the entire process of financial control within the IA operations. There are two major cost considerations of CAE, i.e., employee-related and audit-related budgets¹⁰, which form the core of cost-centered planning. It is advised to separate budgets for audit-related and non-audit-related services. In this way, CAE could make a periodic cost variance analysis for the cost centers at any stage during the fiscal year and monitor whether individual audits meet their budgets.

In addition, this kind of variance analysis could also provide a reliable basis for future resource and cost planning to achieve efficiency. It is important to record all expenditures and work times of the internal auditors for each audit request for statistical and performance purposes and for potential revenue generation. The major objective could be to widen the basis on which the economic efficiency of IA is measured with regard to budget compliance or to earn a contribution margin.

According to Committee of Sponsoring Organizations (COSO) approach¹¹, IA's objectives and activities should be associated with the strategic objectives of the organization¹². Commonly, IA function must arrange its operations and responsibilities based on the principle that the purpose of all audit activities is ultimately to accomplish these core strategic objectives. IA and the organization should use a risk-based monitoring to support the achievement of these objectives. In this way, it is aimed to achieve a value-added approach in working style and client satisfaction at engagement management.

Kagermann et al. (2008) discussed the objectives of IA in the COSO framework and divided these objectives into two groups (as shown in Figure 2): strategic objectives and operational objectives. In addition to the key audit-related objectives, IA could also practice other operational and non-audit-related objectives within an organization that involvements in internal projects are as an observer, expert reviews of newly-designed systems, as well as the active initiation of solution steps, such as developing guidelines. The objectives of IA are shown in Figure 2.

It is a fact that audit work produces significant factual knowledge and effective and efficient recommendations to business problems. A centralized coordination and organization of IA help to make best practice solutions available in a database that is maintained by IA. For that reason, IA is also increasingly called upon to conduct benchmarking analyses with value-added content for the top management. The IIA's code of ethics¹³ leads internal auditors in their efforts to sustain the soundness and effectiveness of an entity's RM, internal control, and corporate governance activities through four fundamental values: (1) integrity; (2) objectivity (along with organizational independence); (3) confidentiality; and (4) competency.

The IIA Research Foundation (2011) recommended the following key points for a leading practice in optimizing an IA function:

- (1) It is important to ensure that the CAE is well-connected at the executive level;
- (2) Internal auditors should be cautious about building relationships based on trust so that the IA team is seen as a collaborator rather than a policeman;
- (3) Internal auditors spend more time in understanding the operations, strategy, and strategic initiatives of management throughout the audit process to enhance the governance framework;

¹⁰ Important considerations include training and development, travel expenses, as well as audit literature, costs for expert opinions, the involvement of external specialists, and attendance at professional conferences.

¹¹ Please refer to COSO website (<http://www.coso.org>) for further details.

¹² These three primary objectives of the organization, as defined in the COSO internal control framework, are as follows: (1) compliance with laws and regulations; (2) reliability of financial reporting; and (3) operational efficiency and profitability.

¹³ Please refer to IIA website (<http://www.theiia.org>) for more detailed information.

(4) Staffing strategy of IA teams should be carefully established with people who have experience in other parts of the organization;

(5) It is essential to encourage and/or mandate training and professional development activities periodically to cover the risk profile of the organization (develop plans to address any gaps identified);

(6) CAE should spend some time in interviewing members of management to get their specific views and feedback on the skills and knowledge of the audit staff and to identify topics that may need addressing;

(7) It is needed to arrange a quality assessment review of IA function to assure its soundness to identify causes and implement remedies.

Figure 2. Objectives of IA. Source: Kagermann et al. (2008).

Concluding Remarks

It is a fact that management is responsible for maintaining sufficient internal control systems to manage risks within the organization. IA provides assurance services to management, the board of directors, and the audit committee based on reviewing the adequacy of these internal control systems. IA also provides a consulting role in promoting and facilitating the improvement of effective systems of RM and internal control. Subject to the content of IA charter and availability of resources, IA may respond to management's requests for investigations into matters of fraud, probity, and compliance.

IA makes recommendations on addressing these problems, which remain the responsibility of management. Furthermore, IA shall have no responsibilities over the operations. In other words, the IA activity should contribute to the organization's governance process by evaluating and improving the process through which: (1) Values and goals are established and communicated; (2) The accomplishment of goals is monitored;

(3) Accountability is ensured; and (4) Values are preserved.

Today, modern IA functions widen their activities to all operational areas of the organization and have positioned themselves as valued and respected parts of the senior management effort. They are formally and actively reporting to the board of directors and the audit committee. This overall situation reflects major progress in the scope of IA's coverage and level of service to all areas of the organization. The internal auditing profession itself has contributed to this progress through its own self-improvement and enthusiasm. In that respect, it is expected that IA functions will set the stage for a continuing upward trend with a value-added approach. It is also noted in IIA survey results that both independence and objectivity are viewed as key factors for IA activities to add value.

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